
**D4.16 Report from
supportive start-up
meeting, 2nd round**
Workpackage 4
Joint Integrative Projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: BfR, SCIENSANO

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D4.16 Report from supportive start-up meeting, 2 nd round
WP and Task	WP4, task 4.2.1 Start-up support
Leader	SVA
Other contributors	BfR, SCIENSANO, PMT
Due month of the deliverable	M25
Actual submission month	M25
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

REPORT FROM SUPPORTIVE START-UP MEETING, 2ND ROUND

Background

To provide initial support to the thirteen Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and the three Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) of the OHEJP 2nd call, starting in January 2020, a kick-off meeting was held in Berlin on 13 November 2019. The JRP and JIP project leaders, their deputy project leaders or other representatives from the projects were invited to the meeting, which was organized and hosted by WP5 (Annemarie Käsbohrer, BfR) and coordinated by WP3 (Hein Imberechts, SCIENSANO), with participation of WP4 (Karin Artursson, SVA), WP1 (Arnaud Callegari, ANSES) and the Communication team (Jade Passey, UoS).

The purpose of the kick-off meeting was to provide the new projects with information about the OHEJP itself, its main objectives and structure, where to find support on different aspects, general project management and the expectations on the projects in terms of e.g. reporting and setting up a data management plan. An additional aim of the meeting was to provide the project leaders with an opportunity to meet and network. This interaction between projects is very important for future success of the projects.

Invitation

An invitation to the meeting was sent out to the JRP and JIP project leaders by the Coordination team on 8 October 2019, with the following information:

"The Coordination Team of the OneHealth EJP is happy to invite you to the kick-off meeting of the second call projects.

This meeting will take place on 13th November 2019 in the Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung in Berlin.

The objective of this meeting is to inform all project representatives about the OneHealth EJP itself, the management and reporting of the joint research and integrative projects, financial and ethics issues, communication and dissemination procedures and the need for a data management plan. The scope of the meeting is detailed in the scope note attached.

As you can see in the agenda enclosed, at the meeting, every new project will briefly (in 5 minutes, pitch presentations, see template enclosed) be presented. Representatives of ECDC and EFSA will participate at the meeting, which gives them the opportunity to get familiar with the OHEJP activities in the coming years.

For these reasons, we invite all Project Leaders or/and their deputy to take part in this meeting. Please note that you are also invited to attend the diner planned the evening before (12th of November 2019).

Please confirm your attendance at both the November 13th meeting and the November 12th dinner via: <https://onehealthejp.eu/event/one-health-ejp-joint-research-and-joint-integrative-project-kick-off-meeting/>

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

We do thank you to forward this invitation to register to your deputy, or any other person who intends to attend the meeting.

Please also be advised that travel and accommodation costs are eligible and will be covered by the OHEJP budget, even if your project has not yet started.

As noticed in the leaflet note attached, this kick-off meeting is organized by Annemarie Kaesbohrer and Ludo Sepe from the BfR (in cc).

We do hope that you will find this opportunity to meet useful and that you, and/or your deputy can be present.”

Agenda

The agenda included the following items:

12 November 2019

19:30 – 22:00 Social event: Dinner
Brauhaus Lemke am Schloss - LUISENPLATZ 1 10585 BERLIN-CHARLOTTENBURG

13 November 2019

10:00 - 10:15 Welcome and introduction of attendees (Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Karin Artursson and Hein Imberechts)
10:15 - 12:00 Elevator pitch/short introduction of 2nd call projects (All project representatives) DiSCoVeR, BIOPIGEE, TOXOSOURCES, ADONIS, BeONE, FARMED, Worldcom, Full-Force, FED-AMR, TELE-Vir, IDEMBRU, MEME, PARADISE, CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP and MATRIX.
12:00 - 12:45 Lunch
12:45 - 13:15 General introduction OneHealth EJP (Hein Imberechts)
13:15 - 14:00 JRP & JIP: Reporting, ethics, DMP, dissemination, publication policy, etc. (Hein Imberechts a.o.)
14:00 - 14:15 Coffe Break
14:15 - 14:45 Integrative activities (Karin Artursson)
14:45 - 15:30 Financial issues (Arnaud Callegari)
15:30 - 16:00 Communication (Jade Passey)
16:00 End of meeting

Action points

1. Upon request by one of the PLs, some modifications in the nearly finalized Scientific Publication Policy were considered. This was followed up by WP4.
2. Stef Bronzwaer from EFSA emphasised the importance of the implementation of project results. He also pointed out that the impact of outcomes has to be measured. This point will be followed up on by the PMT and additional integrative activities for the dissemination of results and outcomes will be presented within shortly.
3. Data Management Plans have to be set up and submitted from all projects. Géraldine Boseret at Sciensano is the contact point and will assist to answer any questions in relation to this.
4. A question was raised by a PL how the OHEJP partners can be sure that EC co-financing will be available and thus can start the recruitment. According to Arnaud Callegari this is covered by the grant agreement. Thus all approved projects can start the recruitment.

Participants

Name	Partner
1. Arnaud Callegari	ANSES
2. Noëlie Colinet	ANSES
3. Claire Ponsart	ANSES
4. Stef Bronzwaer	EFSA
5. Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden	Roskilde University
6. Werner Ruppitsch	AGES
7. Hein Imberechts	Sciensano
8. Pieter-Jan Ceyskens	Sciensano
9. Géraldine Boseret	Sciensano
10. Elke Burrow	BfR
11. Chris Kollas	BfR
12. Annemarie Käsbohrer	BfR
13. Ludovico Sepe	BfR
14. Matthias Filter	BfR
15. Esther Sundermann	BfR
16. Katja Leicht	BfR
17. Saskia Mewes	BfR
18. Tine Hald	DTU
19. Sofia Duarte	DTU
20. Suzanne Karlsrose Pedersen	DTU
21. Kristoffer Kiil	SSI
22. Jeppe Boel	SSI
23. Katrin Gaardbo Kuhn	SSI
24. Flemming Scheutz	SSI
25. Nadia Boisen	SSI
26. Maiken Rosenstjerne	SSI
27. Pikka Jokelainen	SSI
28. Manal AbuOun	APHA
29. Nicholas Duggett	APHA
30. Jade Passey	UoS
31. Louise O'Connor	NUIG
32. Terry Smith	NUIG
33. Simone Cacciò	ISS
34. Adriano Casulli	ISS
35. Alberto Mantovani	ISS
36. Eelco Franz	RIVM
37. Claudia Coipan	RIVM
38. Lapo Mughini-Gras	RIVM
39. Michael Brouwer	WBVR
40. Wim van der Poel	WBVR
41. Joukje Siebenga	WBVR
42. Dariusz Wasyl	PIWET
43. Karin Artursson	SVA
44. Marie Nykvist	SVA
45. Karin Troell	SVA

Presentations

All presentations, including the project pitch presentations are provided in the Appendix.